

Evaluating Machine's Ability To Generate Thoughts

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In this work, the ability of a machine to generate an original thought as opposed to its ability to reason is presented as a form of human-like intelligence in which the machine doesn't have to replicate all human cognitive abilities as in the case of Artificial General Intelligence, AGI. Moreover, a simple test is proposed to evaluate a machine's ability to generate an original thought.

Key words:

Machine; Thought Generation; Reasoning; AGI; Test

Suppose a machine passes the [Turing Test](#) by showing intelligence through engaging in a conversation with a human judge who can't distinguish it from another human.

Moreover, suppose that a machine was able to make its decisions through learning as suggested by Turing's analogy between a human child, who learns the spirit of initiative and decision-making, and a simple machine, or what Turing called the "[child machine](#)," which learns through basic instructions.

Still there is a challenge for such a machine to achieve Artificial General Intelligence, [AGI](#), which is defined by its ability to replicate all aspects of human intelligence. This work suggests that this definition isn't obligatory for a machine to compete with human intelligence as it could achieve a higher form of intelligence through being able to generate an original thought.

A simple means of evaluating whether a machine is able to generate an original thought could be through measuring the possibility of extracting a sentence out of the context of an [LLM](#) conversation that would still hold meaning as a standalone sentence. A condition for such an experiment is that this sentence doesn't represent a quote itself.

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